

Social Economic Impact of Culinary Street Vendor Relocation From Jalan Yos Sudarso to Sangumang Culinary Park Kota Palangka Raya

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ABSTRACT: *The purposes of this study are to describe the culinary street vendor relocation process, the socio-economic impact of culinary street vendor relocation, the supporting factors and inhibitors of culinary street vendor relocation at Yos Sudarso Street, Palangka Raya City to Sangguma culinary park. The method used is descriptive qualitative in which the data are collected through interviews, observations and documentations then the data are analyzed through the stages of collection, reduction, presentation. Finally, the conclusion can be drawn. The results of this study show that the process of relocating the culinary street vendors is still not optimal as it is expected because the culinary street vendors have not yet moved to the new places (Sangumang Single Culinary Park) until now. This relocation makes culinary street vendors uneasy because there are other new culinary street vendors who enter to the new relocation site. The social impacts of culinary street vendor relocation in at Jalan Yos Sudarso, Palangka Raya City, are as follows: in the comfortable point of view, culinary street vendors feel more comfortable. From terms of security, the place is safe, although when the rainy day there is a mild flood. From the income point of view, the majority of culinary street vendor income is decreasing because there is no empowerment from the government. The government also has problems in relocating culinary street vendors because of the land limitation and the mindset of culinary street vendors who are still comfortable to trade at the shoulder of the road because there is no rent for the place.*

KEYWORDS - *Culinary Street Vendor*

I. INTRODUCTION

Jalan Yos Sudarso The city of Palangka Raya is famous for its culinary center, where there are various types of culinary, which usually starts in the afternoon. the culinary street vendors opens their stalls or sales in the afternoon. In fact, the government policy that culinary street vendors will be relocated from Jalan Yos Sudarso to Jalan Bukit Kaminting intersection which will later be made a special place for culinary street vendors at the same time be a culinary tour by the Palangka Raya Government is still not optimal.

Culinary street vendor relocation aims to create the beauty of the City especially about layout and implementation of development in urban areas. In addition, this is an attempt by the City government to keep the green open space in Yos Sudarso road area clean, tidy, not seedy, orderly and comfortable so as not to disturb road users. However, the relocation that has been carried out by the Palangka Raya Government still leaves the problem that the traders who had been trading for a long time along Yos Sudarso Street are not concerned about the place in the new relocation area, namely on Jalan Bukit Kaminting intersection because of the presence of new traders taking part too.

Culinary street vendor (PKL) as one of the economic drivers in Palangka Raya City is good enough to contribute to the Palangka Raya City's Local Revenue (PAD). It is expected that the arrangement carried out by the Municipal Government can accommodate all the old culinary vendors, so that they do not seem to have been evicted, but actually relocated. This relocation is based on Palangka Raya City Government Regulation Number 4 of 2014 concerning Regulation, Control, and Supervision of Field Creative Traders.

Relocating of culinary street vendors to new places is often carried out by the government, however the relocation decisions are often unilateral. So that the income of culinary street vendors plummets and causes new

problems. As a result, culinary street vendors return to their original place or look for other, more promising locations.

The relocation carried out by the City Government of Palangka Raya, which was carried out from 2016 to 2018, has not yet been able to work, while nowadays, culinary street vendors are allowed to sell in the Pasar Datah area, with the possibility that the income generated is not the same as when selling at their original places, while waiting for the Yos Sudarso area at the end of the Jalan Bukit Kaminting intersection to be ready for use.

Several studies on street vendors have been carried out for cities in Indonesia including Murtanti Jani Rahayu, Isti Andini, Rufia Andisetyana Putri (Surabaya 2015), urban street vendors, known as street vendors in Surakarta, have experienced a series of structuring strategies in the form of relocation and stabilization. In relocating street vendors is expected to provide convenience for street vendors. Umami Hanifah, Mussadun (Semarang 2014), The implementation of street vendor relocation is considered difficult to implement due to rejection and considers Pasar Waru not representative to trade. Whereas the implementation of Simpang Lima street vendor arrangement is quite smooth. But after the arrangement, the merchant's income actually declined. Based on the analysis, it is known that according to traders and the relocation government has succeeded in the physical aspect but has not succeeded in the economic aspect. Aloysius Gunadi BRATA (Yogyakarta 2007), the study found that most street vendors in Yogyakarta experienced vulnerability at the secondary level. In general, the vulnerability of food sellers is higher than other vendors. Vulnerability also varies in various sales locations.

Yandi Andri Yatmo (Depok 2008), the existence of street vendors have become a problematic problem in many countries. Despite various arguments that support or reject their presence in urban environments, street vendors are generally accused of disturbing environmental order and therefore must be removed. The arguments in this paper reconsider the position of street vendors in cities in Indonesia, referring to Mary Douglas's theory of 'getting out of place'. As a reassessment of street vendors as an urban element 'out of place' offers a theoretical foundation for urban design and planning practices in dealing with certain undesired elements.

Based on the case or phenomenon, the authors are interested in writing-related research how the process of relocating culinary street vendors in Yos Sudarso Street, Palangka Raya City, how the socio-economic impact of culinary street vendors after relocation in Jalan Yos Sudarso, and what are the supporting factors and inhibitors of culinary street vendor relocation.

Social change

Social change is a form of change in humanity due to the escalation of natural, biological, physical changes that occur throughout human life. (Agus Salim, 2002: 1) Social change can be imagined as changes that occur within or encompass social systems. More precisely, there are differences between the state of a particular system in different time periods. Speaking of change, according to Strasser & Randel quoted by Piotr Szotompka (2008; 3), namely by imagining something that happens after a certain period of time; deal with differences in circumstances observed between before and after a certain period of time. To get the difference, the initial features of the unit of analysis must be known carefully even though they continue to change. So the basic concept of social change encompasses three ideas, namely differences, different times and between the same state of the social system.

Social change according to Gillin and Gillin in Soerjono Soekanto (2007: 263) is as a variation of the ways of life that have been received, both because of changes in geographical conditions, culture, population composition, ideology and because of the diffusion or new discoveries in society. Samuel Koenig briefly says that social change refers to the modifications that occur in patterns of human life that occur due to internal causes and external causes.

Social change can be divided into several types, depending on the angle of observation: whether in terms of aspects, fragments or dimensions of the social system. This is due to the state of the social system that is not simple, not only a single dimension but appears as a combination or combination of the results of the state of the component as follows:

1. The basic elements, which consist of the number, type of individual and community action.
2. Relations between elements, namely social ties, loyalty, dependence, individual relations, and integration.
3. The functioning of elements in the system, for example, the role of work played by individuals or the need for certain actions to preserve social order.
4. Boundary maintenance, namely the criteria for determining who belongs to the system members, the requirements for individual acceptance in the group, the principle of recruitment in the organization, and so on.
5. Subsystem, which consists of the number and type of sections, segments, or special divisions that can be distinguished.

6. Environment, namely natural conditions or geopolitical location.

Socio-Economic Impact

Etymologically the impact means violations, collisions, or collisions, while a sociological approach can be interpreted as the use of basic concepts to examine a social phenomenon in the sense that social impacts are an effect of social phenomena that occur in people's lives.

Socio-economic impacts can be seen from the positive and negative sides so that they can be more balanced in providing an assessment. Some positive things are increasing business feasibility and convenience, opening employment opportunities, changing the status of being a legal trader. Negative impacts are decreasing income, increasing operational costs, weakening social networks, and decreasing opportunities for traders to participate in non-formal social groups (Sinaga, 2004: 134). Meanwhile, according to Djojodipuro (1992: 194), the socio-economic impact is a change that occurs in society due to development activities that affect changes in income, business opportunities, and employment. This socio-economic impact occurs in the economic system which involves economic structure and conditions. Socio-economic impacts are all things related to meeting the needs in the community or more generally related to the welfare of the community (Zunaidi, 2013).

Relocation

Relocation is the transfer of a place to a new place. Relocation is one manifestation of the local government policy included in the revitalization activities. Relocation is an effort to transfer street vendors (PKL) businesses which includes relocation preparation activities and relocation implementation to the new place. (Palangka Raya City Regional Regulation No. 4 the Year 2013).

According to Binsar M. Gulton in Lusiani (2008: 14) said that in general the notion of relocation is often interpreted simply as a displacement in terms of geographical space. Even though it cannot be denied that relocation involves the struggle between various spatial concepts such as economic, social, political, and environmental spaces to the cultural space. Whereas According to F. Davidson in Lusiani (2008: 14) said that the location and quality of new relocation sites are important factors in relocation planning because it determines things such as ease of going to business, social networks, employment, business, credit, and market opportunity. Each location has its own limitations and opportunities. Choosing the same location with the area that previously in terms of environmental, social, cultural and economic characteristics will enable more successful relocation and income recovery.

II. METHODOLOGY

This type of descriptive qualitative research describes the phenomena and facts that occur in the social impact of street vendor relocation. Data collection techniques are carried out by means of observation, interviews, and documentation (Sugiyono, 2013: 205). The research informants consisted of seven people, Mr. Sirko, Bp Ali Imron, Bp. Agus, Bp Yuharsono, Bp. Mustofa, Bp. Sarijo, Bp. Supri. Data analysis in this study there is four activities that occur simultaneously, namely data that has been collected is read, studied and summarized. After data reduction is performed in the form of brief descriptions, charts, and narrative texts. Furthermore, conclusions are drawn up supported by valid and consistent evidence.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Culinary Street Vendor (PKL) Relocation Process in Jalan Yos Sudarso, Palangka Raya City

Relocation carried out by Pemko Palangka Raya with the aim of rearranging the city of Palangka Raya to make it look beautiful and neat by relocating culinary street vendors to a new place namely Jalan Yos Sudarso intersection Jalan Bukit Kaminting by making a new area for culinary street vendors as a culinary tour of Palangka Raya City.

The culinary street vendor relocation effort placed at Jalan Yos Sudarso on the Bukit Kaminting intersection is as a Government effort to follow up the "Beautiful City" to organize the city area.

This policy is made by the government with the aim of providing business opportunities for culinary street vendors through the determination of location in accordance with its designation; grow and develop the culinary PKL business capabilities into a strong and independent micro-economic business; to create a city that is clean, beautiful, order, and safe with adequate urban facilities and infrastructure. So that the arrangement of

culinary street vendors has several stages/processes carried out before the culinary street vendors are placed to the new location that is intended for culinary street vendors.

The Head of Structuring and Aesthetics Division, Palangka Raya City Housing and Settlement Area, stated that the new relocation site of a street vendor (Jalan PK Sud) Yos Sudarso was still relatively strategic, so he hoped that the street vendors would not worry about their business will turn drop if it is relocated.

According to Pak Imbang: "The new location is still strategic even though it is a bit far from the city. In addition, we will also prepare special stalls for hundreds of culinary street vendors," So the government hope that for culinary street vendors are free about this relocation because every culinary street vendors will get a place to trade back as promised by the Government.

According to the Head of the Public Housing and Settlement Area of Palangka Raya City, Rawang Relocation will be carried out in two stages. Where stage I for 50 culinary street vendors. Then, for this year phase II for 20 culinary street vendors. "To realize this, we will procure containers that will be used as culinary vendors' stalls," said Rawang while giving a speech at the inauguration of six parks within the City of Palangka Raya.

Rawang asserted that the provision of container stalls would later be given to PKL by being drawn, but it is prioritized to those who were relocated due to the construction of the Yos Sudarso Park from the large roundabout of TVRI Central Kalimantan.

In this culinary street vendor relocation program, it also will not accommodate the desire of residents who want to rent container stalls whose purpose is to rent again. His party only accommodates residents who rent and sell.

Based on the explanation above that this relocation is a program from the City Government of Palangka Raya in the Making of City Park in the area of Yos Sudarso Street for that impact on the culinary street vendors who sell around the street, the government will provide new places to culinary street vendors namely Yos Sudarso Street Jalan Bukit Kaminting intersection which is called Taman Sangumang. The number of culinary street vendors who will be moved is 70 PKL according to the list of street vendors in the place of origin, namely Jalan Yos Sudarso. In fact, Culinary street vendors worry when the relocation is done they do not get a place to trade because it is due to the presence of new culinary street vendors.

B. Socio-Economic Impact of Culinary Street Vendor Relocation

Social Impact of Culinary Street Vendor Relocation

Culinary street vendors that are moved to a place / relocated must have a lot of consideration about the impact that can arise from the transfer to the new location. In fact, if it is in accordance with the correct procedures and flow, the relocation process will have a positive impact on culinary and government street vendors activities. Conversely, if the relocation is not in accordance with existing procedures and rules, it will have a negative impact on the culinary and government street vendor activities. So there is a need for coordination between the government and culinary street vendors in the process of determining a culinary street vendor location that will affect on the level of comfortable for culinary street vendors in running their business.

In terms of comfort, culinary street vendors indeed feel better and comfortable for selling in the park. Also, the containers are provided as a place to sell and they no longer encourage/unload their selling carts again.

For the key security problem in a new place, it is convenient because the vendor does not have to push carts anymore, install tents, because the new place has provided a place to sell, namely in the form of containers, and one more because the transfer is too far from the city center so many traders worried about the decline in their income results from the information of the culinary street vendors.

In Heriyanto's findings (2012) it was also revealed that relocation by the government must consider the positive and negative impacts on social terms. Because the comfort factor of business is very influential on the level of security, orderliness, cleanliness of the place of sale and purchase of street vendors and the increasing income of street vendors. So that the negative stigma attached to PKL can change by taking part in keeping the city order. As revealed in Rahman's findings (2014) with the relocation, traders assume that the activities carried out by traders become more orderly and safe so it is not to interfere with the beauty of the city order.

Relocation into the park is also expected by the government that PKL is able to care for and maintain the plants in the park so as not to be damaged. Because the park must actually look clean, neat, and beautiful so that the beauty and order of the city are not disturbed. Borrowing the term Sutrisno, et.al (2007: 170) in the concept of street vendors' arrangement that the place of business arrangements for street vendors that guarantee order, security, and beauty of the city, and support government programs make the city a city of culture, tourism, and sports.

Economic Impact of Culinary PKL Relocation

The economic impact of relocation in the area of Yos Sudarso Street which is currently called the Sangumang Single Park (Culinary Park) is seen in terms of income earned by traders before and after relocation. So that the traders with one another have the same motivation to make a living in meeting their daily needs. Economic impacts due to relocation include the level of income, business development and including the business capital of culinary street vendors. In terms of income, after the relocation of the culinary street vendors' income, they still have not been maximized and the majority of their income decreases. Based on the term Djodipuro (1992: 194) socio-economic impacts are changes that occur in society due to development activities that affect changes in income.

"We have been selling here for years. If the government wants to relocate us automatically the government must know how much we can get when selling here. Can the government guarantee we will get the same value even more if we are willing to be relocated?" (Mr. Supri)

Traders claim to be able to get a turnover of around Rp. 650,000 per day or reaching Rp.19 million per month. Even though he only opened a stall only in the afternoon, from 17.00 WIB to 23.00 WIB.

Traders hope that in the new relocation place, their income will not decline from before. Considering that until now the new place is still not be operated or run, for a while the culinary vendors sell in Pasar Datah area, seeing the field conditions usually the relocated culinary street vendors are not always open every day, and this condition has an impact on their turnover per the month.

From the hopes of the culinary PKL above, every relocation can increase the income from culinary street vendors. Not to mention if there is a new place to rent a place or a place to sell, this is a new issue for culinary street vendors who should be able to get a place to sell to not get a place due to limited funds.

For this reason, the Government must also consider the above matters so that in this relocation does not leave a new problem for culinary street vendors. Some street vendors (PKL) have been selling at the location of Sangumang Single Park, Jalan Yos Sudarso on Jalan Bukit Kaminting intersection, but until now the price of container rental has not been determined by the Industry and Trade Office (Perindag) of Palangka Raya City.

According to the Head of the Industry and Trade Office of Palangka Raya City, Aratuni Djaban has not yet determined the rental of the stalls per month. Currently, his service is still formulating the right formula to determine the lapak rental.

There are two formulas that the city government will offer. First, the PKL is enough to rent a lapak with a range of Rp. 800 thousand per month. The second formula, culinary street vendors are asked to buy container stalls with an installment system for several years.

In the findings of Fatnawati (2013) it was also explained that in terms of economics, it is clear that with good management and proper placement, it makes financial benefits, especially for the street vendors themselves and generally the general public who use their services. Research by Setyaningsih and Susilo (2014) also found that traders experienced an increase in income after being relocated. In contrast to the relocation in the culinary park of Sangumang Singles Park, the majority of PKL income decreased by almost 20%. Because the location of the culinary park of Sangumang Singles Park that is occupied by street vendors is currently not yet designated as the location of street vendors, so the empowerment of the government cannot be implemented and accepted by PKL to improve the quality of street vendors' merchandise.

Supporting Factors and Inhibitors of PKL Relocation

The results of research on the relocation of street vendors show that there are supporting and inhibiting factors in its implementation. Supporting factors in the relocation of street vendors in Jalan Yos Sudarso near the Great Roundabout are the socialization of the comfort, security and cleanliness of the street vendors' location, where PKL attracts visitors, the availability of facilities and infrastructure for free to support the level of visitor comfort, rumors of all street vendors selling on the side of the road, there is guidance from the government as a follow-up to relocation. The following is the narrative of one of the informants regarding the supporting factors of the relocation of street vendors in Jalan Yos Sudarso near the Great Roundabout:

"The supporting factor is that the place we provide can be more crowded than the previous place, how we can create the location of the Culinary PKL to attract the attention of visitors because it is quite far from the city center." (Interview results on May 5, 2018).

One of the factors that support the relocation is to socialize the convenience, safety, and cleanliness of the street vendors' location. In Rahman's findings (2014) it is explained that by relocating, there will be no continuous eviction because the place they use for buying and selling activities is considered to disturb security, order and beauty of the city order. In addition, the place provided can attract the attention of visitors to come

and the distance of the old location with the new one is not too far away so that street vendors can still know their whereabouts. As in the findings of Fatmawati (2013) that in the location selection of street vendors here is influenced by ease of achievement, ease of viewing and ease of relationship with formal activities. So as to make it easier for customers to access the existence and time of the street vendors starting to sell their merchandise.

However, researchers found inhibiting factors in street vendors relocation such as land not available for street vendors, education to the community to participate in managing the city was still minimal, the budget for street vendors relocation was still limited, there was no solution for street vendors relocation, and street vendors' mindset that was already comfortable selling in their original place so they do not want to be moved. The following is the narrative of the speakers regarding one of the inhibiting factors of street vendor relocation in the area of Jalan Yos Sudarso near the Big Roundabout of Palangka Raya City:

"Education to the community is still minimal because community involvement to organize a clean city is also very large. Limited budget problems, and where there is no land, culinary street vendors' mindset that is more convenient to sell on the road because it does not pay, is not burdened with rent."
"(Interview results on May 6, 2018).

In the same word, it can be concluded that the inhibiting factors in culinary street vendors relocation are the available land to relocate culinary street vendors. This is due to the limited budget from the government to relocate culinary street vendors. As a result, the relocation of culinary street vendors is done by simply moving the culinary street vendors, without thinking about the impact in social or economic aspects.

Relocating culinary street vendors is not as easy as turning the palm of the hand because the culinary street vendors that are already comfortable in their original places are one of the culinary PKL inhibitors that do not want to be relocated. Even though the land has been provided by the government, it does not guarantee that the culinary street vendors will move to the new place. This is because the fear of culinary street vendors in decreasing their income. The other is the comfortable of culinary street vendors sell on the shoulder of the road and crowd of visitors. The culinary street vendors' mindset and buyers (community) who want to be free and practical in carrying out buying and selling activities are obstacles to the Government relocating.

Implications and recommendations

Relocating culinary street vendors must be in a line with the rules that have been set. Discretionary steps should be taken if the solution to relocate the culinary street vendors is no longer obtained. So, it is expected that the relocation carried out a positive impact on social and economic aspects.

Relocating should first provide a new relocation place before relocating the culinary street vendors. If the new place is ready, then the culinary street vendors will be relocated, the relocation can be done. In fact, the researchers see the situation in the field that the culinary street vendors are placed in a place that finally troubles the culinary street vendors and until now there are still those who sell at Palangka Raya Park, even though the place is already there is no longer any culinary street vendors there.

A relocation that is carried out should not just move to a new location and only provide shelter to sell, but also the facilities to attract the attention of buyers are needed, such as tents for the seat of the buyer, repair of the water channel, and the installation so as not to tarnish when it rains. Culinary PKL should take part in training conducted by the government to improve the quality of its merchandise such as the packaging used to present or wrap its wares to make it more attractive.

It is hoped that there will be greater attention from the government to reduce or even eliminate the factors that hinder the development of the culinary street vendors in the area of Yos Sudarso Street, Palangka Raya City. Preparing the container stalls according to the number of culinary street vendors who will be relocated so that all get a place to sell again. Conduct persuasive and periodic education to the community and culinary PKL itself so as not to conduct trading activities in places that are prohibited by the Regulation. Data collection and registration of culinary street vendors must immediately be socialized and requirements needed to be distributed to legalize the status of culinary street vendors.

IV. CONCLUSION

- A. Relocation in the area of Yos Sudarso Street in Palangka Raya City has not been maximized because the implementation process could not run smoothly, causing anxiety for culinary street vendors because they were afraid of not getting a stall in a new place due to the new culinary street vendors grabbing stalls to sell.
- B. The social impact of culinary street vendor relocation in the area of Yos Sudarso Street, Palangka Raya City, in terms of comfort, namely the culinary street vendors are more comfortable because the place has

been provided by the government on condition of paying rent or buying it in installments or cash. In terms of security, a new place that is safe is only a little constrained if it rains, the parking area will experience flooding. In terms of cleanliness, this place is clean because it is designed to sell for culinary street vendors by providing containers as a place to sell. Whereas the economic impact felt by the culinary street vendors in the area of Yos Sudarso Street, Palangka Raya City, in terms of income, the majority decreased by almost 20% because the location was still new and there are just little people coming.

- C. Factors supporting the relocation of culinary street vendors in the Jalan Yos Sudarso City of Palangka Raya are a place of relocation made them easy to attract the attention of visitors and not far from the old place. Next is the availability of extensive parking, so buyers who come feel safe to park their vehicles (no parking on the shoulder of the road). Whereas the relocation inhibiting factor is not too large because the culinary street vendors are willing to be relocated to a new place, only at a new place culinary street vendors have to pay rent for the stall or can buy it. However, the government has not set a price yet until now. Culinary street vendors feel afraid if they move to the new place it will be quiet buyer. In a line, their mindset is still the same. They are more comfortable for trading at the old place/shoulder of the road because there is no rent for the place.

REFERENCES

Journal Papers:

- [1] Purnomo, (2016). Impact of Relocation to the Social Environment of Street Vendors at Pratistha Harsa Culinary Center Purwokerto. *Equilibrium Journal*. Volume 11, Number 1, March 2016. University of Muhammadiyah Ponorogo
- [2] Saputra, (2014). Profile of Street Vendors Selling at the Road Agency (Study on Jalan Teratai and Jalan Seroja District Senapelan). Sociology Department, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences. Volume 1 No. 2 - October 2014. University of Riau

Books:

- [3] Djojodipuro, Marsudi. (1992). *Location Theory*. Jakarta: Institute of Publishers of the Faculty of Economics, University of Indonesia.
- [4] Fatnawati, Nur. (2013). *Impact of Relocation of Street Vendors Based on Surakarta City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2008 concerning Management of Street Vendors Against Street Vendors in Surakarta*. Semarang: Semarang State University
- [5] Palangka Raya City Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2013 concerning Regulation, Control, and Supervision of Field Creative Traders
- [6] Domestic Regulation Number 41 of 2012 concerning Guidelines and Structuring and Empowerment of Street Vendors.
- [7] Rahman, Abdul. (2014). *The Impact of Squatting of Street Vendors (PKL) Squat Markets to MTC Giant Panam Against the Socio-Economic Life of Traders*. Pekanbaru: University of Riau.
- [8] Sugiyono. (2013). *Qualitative, Quantitative and R & D Research Methods*. Bandung: Alfabeta
- [9] Soekanto, Soerjono. (1983). *Sociological Theory of Social Change*. Surabaya: Ghalia Indonesia.